

Evaluation of Beverage Companies Operating on the Istanbul Stock Exchange Using the Ratio Analysis Method

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Abstract: This study evaluates the financial performance of five publicly traded beverage companies on Borsa Istanbul by using ratio analysis. Financial data from 2016 to 2020 were obtained through the Public Disclosure Platform (KAP), Data Analysis Platform (VAP), and official company websites. Key financial ratios - liquidity, profitability, activity, and indebtedness - were calculated and compared with industry averages from VAP to assess firm performance. Ratio analysis, a widely used financial analysis method, allows for the comparison of various financial statement items to industry benchmarks, competitors, and historical data. It helps stakeholders make informed decisions by identifying operational strengths and weaknesses. The findings indicate notable differences in performance among the companies analyzed. Coca-Cola and Kristal Kola led in liquidity ratios. Coca-Cola showed the strongest performance in activity and profitability ratios, while Kristal Kola stood out in financial structure ratios. However, no single company demonstrated excellence across all categories. The study findings provide investors and financial decision makers with comprehensive information on the strengths and weaknesses of the companies in the sector and enable them to make more informed decisions through sectoral evaluations and comparisons. Considering the strategic importance of the sector in the Turkish economy and its foreign trade potential, it is emphasised that such studies provide guidance both at investment and policy levels.

Keywords: BIST (Borsa Istanbul A.Ş.), ratio analysis, liquidity ratios, activity ratios, financial structure ratios, profitability ratios.

1. INTRODUCTION

Along with food products, beverage products are one of the basic needs of people. Beverage products, which meet the energy needs of individuals, provide hydration and become social consumption habits, have gained importance as commercial products with industrialisation (Çelik, E., Sandal, E. K. & Ayata, V. 2025). The food sector, which is accepted as one of the industries with the most important socio-economic factors of today, stands out as a complex branch of activity that includes many sub-branches and has shown a great development in our country in recent years (Bulu et al., 2007: 311). A high-value sector with a close connection to the agricultural, industrial, and service sectors is the beverage business. Turkey's beverage sector produces a broad variety of goods, including fruit juices, mineral waters, natural spring waters, and alcoholic and non-alcoholic drinks. In terms of both prospective exports and internal consumption, this industry is significant to the Turkish economy (<https://www.tarimorman.gov.tr>).

- Value Added and its Share in Industry: The beverage industry is located in the food and beverage manufacturing sub-sector and provides significant added value to the national economy with its high-tech production infrastructure. The beverage sector, which constitutes approximately 10-15 per cent of the food industry, uses modern production techniques and has a high level of productivity, especially through large-scale companies (<https://www.sanayi.gov.tr/assets/pdf/plan-program/GidaveIcecekSektorRaporu2020.pdf>).

- Contribution to Employment: The sector provides employment to a significant number of people directly and indirectly. Since production facilities are generally located in rural or semi-urban areas, it also contributes to regional development. It also has a strong synergy with the agricultural sector due to production based on agricultural products. In Turkey, the food, beverage and tobacco sector constitutes an important part of the economy and creates employment (Tepeli and Bayrakdaroğlu, 2023: 68).

- Foreign Trade and Brand Power: Turkey's export capacity in products such as fruit juice, mineral water and bottled water has increased over the years. Exports to European, Middle Eastern and Asian markets strengthen the sector's potential to generate foreign currency inflows. Moreover, the establishment of production and export bases in Turkey by multinational companies such as Coca-Cola İçecek increases know-how and technology transfer in the sector.

- Consumer Demand and Market Dynamics: Young population, increase in urbanisation rate, growth in tourism sector and changing consumer habits directly affect beverage

consumption. New product categories such as soft drinks, energy drinks and functional drinks keep the market dynamic and encourage R&D investments of companies.

- Financial Structure of the Sector and its Position in Borsa Istanbul: Beverage firms traded on Borsa Istanbul increase the level of transparency and institutionalisation in the sector. These firms generally have high profitability ratios, strong brand value and export potential. The representation of the sector on the stock exchange creates an alternative value investment area for investors. The beverage sector has a structure that supports the agriculture-based industry, creates employment, has a high export capacity and is constantly growing. With these characteristics, it is a strategic sector that contributes to the sustainable growth and development targets of the Turkish economy. In this study, the following companies in the beverage and dairy products sector traded on Borsa Istanbul, Coca-Cola İçecek A.Ş., Ersu Meyve ve Gıda Sanayi A.Ş., Kristal Kola ve Meşrubat Sanayi Tic. A.Ş., Pınar Su ve İçecek A.Ş. and Pınar Süt Mamülleri Sanayii A.Ş. between the years 2016-2020 with the ratio analysis method.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

With financial ratio analyses, business owners and managers have the opportunity to see whether they have achieved their predetermined targets and how they are doing compared to the sector they are in. Investors can evaluate the situation of the enterprises they will invest in by means of the aforementioned analysis method and decide whether to invest or not. Those who will lend to enterprises can also decide whether or not to extend credit by evaluating the situation with financial ratio analysis. In many different sectors, performance evaluations of firms have been made with the help of ratio analyses. There are various studies in the literature on the beverage sector, which constitutes the scope of the study.

Financial ratio analysis is one of the basic financial analysis methods that enables the evaluation of the financial position of firms by converting the data in the financial statements of firms into certain ratios. Ratio analysis is widely used to quantitatively analyse the liquidity, profitability, operating efficiency and solvency of companies (Brigham & Houston, 2014). This method makes it possible to monitor the change of a firm over the years with time series analysis and to make comparisons between firms in similar sectors with cross-sectional analysis (Gitman, 2011).

In many studies on financial ratio analysis in Turkey, comparative performance analyses have been made according to the ratios of firms operating in different sectors. Especially in studies on companies traded on Borsa Istanbul, the impact of financial ratios on investment decisions, sectoral resilience and performance changes during crisis periods have been frequently addressed (Küçükşille & Acar, 2017; Yıldız & Çelik, 2020). In these studies, indicators such as current ratio, acid-test ratio, inventory turnover ratio, debt/equity ratio, net profit margin and return on equity are generally used.

In studies examining the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on sectoral financial performance, it has been determined that the changes in the supply-demand balance of the beverage sector have adverse effects especially on short-term solvency and profitability ratios (Öztürk & Çetin, 2021). However, beverages and dairy products, which are basic consumer goods, were among the sectors that suffered relatively less damage from the pandemic.

In this context, the existing literature reveals that ratio analysis is a powerful method in sectoral performance evaluations and shows that comparing companies in the beverage sector through this analysis would be academically meaningful and contributory. However, the limited number of ratio analyses focusing on the beverage and dairy sector in Turkey increases the importance of this study.

In their study, Soba and Akcanlı (2012) measured the efficiency of the enterprises with the help of ratio analysis for the periods 2006-2011 through 22 enterprises listed in the ISE and operating in the fields of "Food, Beverage and Tobacco" and included in the sample. In the study, acid-test ratio, equity ratio were used as inputs and borrowing ratio, leverage ratio, return on equity, profit margin and net working capital turnover ratio were used as output criteria. As a result of the study, they concluded that 13.6% (3 enterprises) of 22 enterprises were efficient and 86.4% (19 enterprises) were inefficient.

Omağ (2014), in his study, subjected the 2011-2012 unconsolidated balance sheet and income statement of an enterprise operating in the food sector for 41 years to percentage analysis. The changes in the balance sheet and income statement items of the enterprise in the BIST-Food index were analysed. The data obtained led to the conclusion that the enterprise should have a better cash management policy and cost control activities should be carried out more effectively.

Kendirli and Konak (2014) investigated the relationship between the performance of 18 enterprises and working capital management in the study that examined the effect of working capital management on firm performance in terms of enterprises in the food and beverage index. In the study, return on equity and return on assets as performance indicators were added as dependent variables. Independent variables are operating ratios, receivable turnover rate, inventory turnover rate, short-term debt turnover rate and cash conversion rate. The findings indicate that there is a negative relationship between cash conversion rate and receivables turnover rate and between return on equity and return on assets at 10% significance level.

Dağlı and Eker (2016) conducted a comparative analysis of eight-year financial ratios of large and small-scale enterprises in the Turkish food, beverage and tobacco sector. The comparative analysis of the financial ratios calculated for large and small scale enterprises was conducted using Mann Whitney U test. As a result of the comparative analysis, they concluded that there are significant differences in all of the fixed asset turnover, long-term debt, interest coverage and profitability ratios.

Demiriz (2020), in his master's thesis titled "Financial Structure and Analysis of Food Industry Enterprises Traded in Borsa Istanbul (BIST)", the balance sheets and income statements of food industry enterprises whose shares are traded in Borsa Istanbul for the period 2012-2018 were analysed. The financial performance of the enterprises was measured by applying TOPSIS method through financial ratios such as capital structure, profitability and liquidity ratios.

During the period analysed, liquidity analyses in the enterprises showed that there was no liquidity problem throughout the sector, while the financial structure ratios calculated within the scope of the study showed that equity and foreign resources could not be used at effective levels in a significant part of the enterprises. When profitability analyses are evaluated, it is determined that the gross profit margin in BIST food enterprises was 20.43% on average during the period examined.

3. FINANCIAL STATEMENTS and FINANCIAL ANALYSIS

3.1. Financial Statement

Financial Statements can be expressed as statements containing information on the distribution of assets and resources of enterprises, the results of business activities, the emergence processes of profit or loss for the period, organised in accordance with accounting principles and policies within the framework of the General Communiqué on Accounting System Application (MSUGT). In other words, they are the tables that enable the information produced by accounting through recording and classification to be transferred to information users at certain time intervals to help them in their decision-making processes (Akıncı et al., 1995, p. 4).

Financial statements are the tables in which the financial information resulting from the commercial activities of the enterprise in the current activity period is presented within the unique recording system of accounting and the accounting information users can access detailed information about the enterprise through these tables (Akdoğan & Tenker, 2010, p. 13).

The main purpose of financial statements is to provide useful information to stakeholders such as managers, investors, lenders, credit institutions and the public in the decision-making process, to provide useful data to evaluate the cash inflows and outflows that the entity may generate in the future, to provide information about assets, resources and changes in them and the results of operations. In order for the information provided through financial statements to be useful for decision makers, the statements presenting the information should be appropriate, reliable and comparable. Financial statements organised in a way to carry these features can only contribute to the decision-making process of accounting information users (Usta, 2012, p. 90).

3.2. Types of Financial Statements

Financial statements are organised under two headings: basic (balance sheet and income statement) and supplementary (cash flow, change in equity, etc.) statements in the General Communiqué on Accounting System Application (MSUGT). These statements are a complete set of financial statements within the scope of Turkish Accounting Standards 1 (TAS 1) Presentation of Financial Statements;

- Statement of Financial Position
- Statement of Comprehensive Income
- Cash Flow Statement
- Statement of Changes in Equity

- Cost of Sales Statement
- Profit Distribution Table
- Fund Flow Statement
- Footnotes and explanatory notes.

In the following sections of the study, since the companies operating in BIST prepare and publish their financial statements in accordance with TAS 1, the financial statements in TAS 1 will be referred to as financial statements in the standards.

3.2.1. Statement of Financial Position

The statement of financial position is a financial statement showing the assets (current assets and non-current assets) owned by the enterprises on a certain date and the resources used in the financing of these assets (short-term liabilities, long-term liabilities and equity). Through the statement of financial position, information about the assets owned by the entities and the sources from which these assets are obtained are communicated to the stakeholders. The statement of financial position in TAS is called balance sheet in MSUGT (Akdoğan and Tenker, 2007, p. 72).

3.2.2. Statement of Comprehensive Income

It is a financial statement that collectively shows the net profit or net loss of the enterprise at the end of the operating period by comparing all operating or non-operating revenues generated by the enterprises in a certain period (1 January-31 December) with all costs and expenses incurred in the same period. With the income statement, the income generation power of the enterprises can be examined and the activities can be controlled (Kazbek, 2015, p. 101).

The income statement reflects the periodic economic developments of the enterprise and the earning power in the current period in a complete and real way, as well as information about the activities of the enterprise for a period. In this sense, the income statement is a report that reflects the success of the enterprise for the operating period as a whole (Bakır & Şahin, 2008, p. 46).

3.3. Financial Analysis

In order to transform the raw information presented to stakeholders, i.e. investors, management and shareholders through financial statements into useful information to be used in the decision-making process, financial statements should be analysed with the help of analysis techniques. Financial analysis is the process of examining and evaluating the changes in the financial statement items over time, the relationships between the items, the trends they have shown over time in order to evaluate the financial position and financial development of an enterprise with the help of the analysis technique to be used. When evaluating, criteria such as predetermined standards, sector averages or past company data should be used (Sağlam et al., 2021, p. 21).

3.4. Financial Analysis Techniques

Financial statement analysis is performed by determining the links between the account amounts in the financial statements and the direction of change of these links over time and comparing them with predetermined criteria. In general, financial statements analysis can be performed within the framework of basic analysis techniques such as percentage analysis, comparative tables analysis, trend percentages analysis and ratio analysis (Toroslu and Durmuş, 2016, p. 109).

3.4.1. Ratio Analysis

Ratio is the ratio of two items in the financial statements to each other, that is, the simple mathematical expression of the relationship between the account items. Ratio analysis is basically a proportional comparison of at least two groups or classes of data in balance sheets and income statements

Ratio analysis is known as one of the oldest methods used in financial analysis of financial statements. Wiliam H. Beaver first introduced the method of analysing the financial statements of enterprises through ratios in 1966 and thus solving business problems (Uzunlar, 2009, p. 28)

The main purpose of ratio analysis is to calculate the ratios that will provide information about the solvency, financial structure, operating results and the level of efficient and economical use of assets of the enterprise and to determine the current status of the enterprise with the help of these calculated ratios and to make decisions for the future (Bakır & Şahin, 2008, p. 132).

Ratio analysis is a static analysis method in terms of scope since it performs the analysis on the financial statements of a single period of the enterprise. However, more than one period of the enterprise can be evaluated with this analysis method and the years examined can be compared to give dynamism to the method (Kavcıoğlu, 2019, p. 67).

Ratios used in financial analysis can be classified according to different purposes. Based on the data on the statement of financial position and statement of comprehensive income, the ratios used in the analysis can be analysed in four groups.

- Liquidity ratios,
- Activity rates,
- Financial structure ratios,
- Profitability ratios

4. Application

4.1. Research Method

The study's principal mass and sample determination, data collecting and analysis, and ratios that fall under the purview of ratio analysis and are utilized in financial statement analysis are all covered in this section.

4.1.1. Determination of the Main Population and Sample

The main mass of the study consists of 5 firms operating in the food sector in BIST. In this study, Coca-Cola İçecek A.Ş., Ersu Meyve ve Gıda Sanayi A.Ş., Kristal Kola ve Meşrubat Sanayi Tic. A.Ş., Pınar Su ve İçecek A.Ş. and Pınar Süt Mamülleri Sanayii A.Ş. were taken as basis for the evaluation.

4.1.2. Data Collection and Analysis

Within the scope of this study, the 5-year financial statements and comprehensive income statements of 5 beverage companies constituting the main mass for the years 2016-2020 were obtained through the Public Disclosure Platform (PDP). The data required for the calculation of the ratios to be examined within the framework of ratio analysis for the 5-year period of the enterprises were obtained from financial statements that have been independently audited and therefore have high reliability.

The acquired data was moved to a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Within the scope of the ratio analysis financial statement analysis approach, the firms' liquidity ratios, activity ratios, financial structure ratios, and profitability ratios were computed using the data that was transmitted via Excel. Table 1 lists the ratios that must be computed in this situation.

Table 1. Ratios Analysed within the Scope of Ratio Analysis

Liquidity Ratios
Current Ratio = (Total Current Assets) / (Total Short-Term Liabilities)
Quick-Test Ratio = (Total Current Assets - Inventories) / (Total Short-Term Liabilities)
Cash Ratio = (Total Cash and Cash Equivalentents) / (Total Short-Term Liabilities)
Inventory Dependency Ratio = (Total Short-Term Liabilities - Total Cash and Cash Equivalentents) / (Total Inventory)
Activity Ratios
Accounts Receivable Turnover Ratio = (Net Sales) / (Average Trade Receivables)
Trade Payables Turnover Ratio = (Cost of Goods Sold)/(Average Trade Payables)
Inventory Turnover Ratio = (Cost of Goods Sold)/(Average Inventory Total)
Asset Turnover Ratio = (Net Sales)/(Total Assets)

Financial Structure Ratios

Financial Leverage Ratio= Total Foreign Sources/ Total Assets

Financing Ratio = (Total Equity) / (Total Foreign Sources)

Short-Term Foreign Source Ratio = (Total Short-Term Foreign Sources) / (Total Liabilities)

Long-Term Foreign Capital Ratio = (Total Long-Term Foreign Capital) / (Total Liabilities)

Equity Ratio = (Total Equity) / (Total Liabilities)

Fixed Assets/Permanent Capital Ratio = (Total Fixed Assets) / (Total Permanent Capital)

Profitability Ratios

Asset Profitability Ratio = (Net Profit) / (Total Assets)

Sales Profitability Ratio = (Net Profit) / (Net Sales)

Equity Profitability Ratio = (Net Profit) / (Total Equity)

4.2. Research Findings and Evaluation

In this section of the study, the financial statements of the companies selected within the scope of the sample between 2016-2020 are analysed within the scope of ratio analysis and the results obtained are evaluated.

4.2.1. Coca-Cola İçecek A.Ş.
Table 2. Coca-Cola Liquidity Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Current Ratio	2,09	1,38	1,70	1,26	1,77
Acid-Test Ratio	1,74	1,25	1,40	1,02	1,53
Cash Rate	0,98	0,94	0,86	0,80	1,08
Sector Current Ratio	1,85	2,16	1,73	1,76	2,07
Sector Acid-Test Ratio	1,18	1,12	1,04	1,09	1,34
Sector Cash Ratio	0,06	0,22	0,22	0,27	0,57

When the liquidity ratios are evaluated in general, it is seen that the solvency of the enterprise in the short term is sufficient and the liquidity ratios are close to the sector average. There is no stock dependency of the enterprise. The cash ratio of the enterprise is very high. The enterprise can pay almost all of its short-term debts with its existing cash assets. The entity has more cash than short-term payables in the last year. This means that the company holds idle assets.

Table 3. Coca-Cola Operating Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Receivable Turnover	12,13	13,12	14,9	14,46	14,8
Inventory Turnover	8,16	9,97	8,83	8,98	8,95
Trade Payables Turnove	6,44	6,50	6,31	5,64	5,62
Asset Turnover	0,67	0,63	0,76	0,75	0,75

Sector Receivables Turn	7,97	9,08	10,01	8,61	8,65
Sector Inventory Turn	9,13	9,31	7,98	8,03	7,9
Sector Trade Paya. Turn	4,68	6,98	5,03	5,74	6,93
Sector Asset Turnover	1,17	1,12	1,06	0,95	0,91

Operating ratios guide information users in terms of the extent to which the enterprise uses its assets efficiently. When the RT, IT, TPT and asset turnover rate of the enterprise are evaluated, it is seen that the receivables turnover rate is better than the sector average and the enterprise can collect its receivables quickly. Inventory turnover rate is at the level of sector average. The fact that the trade payables turnover rate is lower than the receivables turnover rate can be said that the enterprise follows a shorter-term receivables policy than the loan maturity provided to it. This situation indicates that receivables can be collected in a shorter period of time and trade payables can be paid.

Table 4. Coca-Cola Financial Structure Ratios

Years	FLR	FR	ER	STFS	LTFS	FA/PCR	Sector FLR	Sector FR	Sector ER	Sector STFS	Sector LTFS	Sector FA/PCR
2016	0,52	0,92	0,48	0,14	0,38	0,82	0,69	1,69	0,63	0,49	0,2	0,75
2017	0,59	0,68	0,41	0,31	0,29	0,83	0,73	1,66	0,62	0,49	0,23	0,7
2018	0,54	0,85	0,46	0,19	0,35	0,84	0,73	1,27	0,56	0,51	0,21	0,77
2019	0,54	0,86	0,46	0,22	0,32	0,93	0,65	1,14	0,55	0,52	0,24	0,76
2020	0,54	0,84	0,46	0,23	0,32	0,77	0,64	1,56	0,65	0,49	0,22	0,77

The use of resources in asset acquisition of the enterprise was close to each other in terms of foreign and equity resources. According to the sector company averages, the enterprise has kept its financing structure strong by preferring financing with more equity. In economic crisis environments, enterprises with a high proportion of equity in their financing structure are more resistant to economic crises. The importance of this was better understood during the Covid 19 pandemic period.

Table 5. Coca-Cola Profitability Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Asset Profitability	0,0045	0,0517	0,0558	0,1275	0,1509
Equity Profitability	0,002	0,021	0,026	0,059	0,069
Sales Profitability	0,003	0,034	0,034	0,078	0,092
Sector Asset Profit.	0,125	0,11	0,134	0,234	0,22
Sector Equity Profit	0,05	0,053	0,06	0,081	0,138
Sector Sales Profit.	0,06	0,057	0,065	0,11	0,128

While liquidity ratios, activity ratios and financial structure ratios were better than the sector averages, profitability ratios were relatively lower. Although the increase in profitability ratios over time was realised in all profitability ratios, it remained below the sector average. It can be said that the Covid 19 pandemic had an impact on this situation.

4.2.2. Ersu Meyve ve Gıda Sanayi A.Ş.

Table 6. Ersu Liquidity Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Current Ratio	4,41	1,7	1,73	2,21	2,47
Acid-Test Ratio	1,59	0,31	0,71	0,74	0,58
Cash Rate	0,01	0,01	0,03	0,02	0,03
Sector Current Ratio	1,85	2,16	1,73	1,76	2,07
Sector Acid-Test Ratio	1,18	1,12	1,04	1,09	1,34
Sector Cash Ratio	0,06	0,22	0,22	0,27	0,57

The current ratio of the company is high compared to the sector average. This indicates that the company can pay its debts in the short term. The rate of return to cash of trade receivables and inventories, which have low liquidity within current assets, is important. As a matter of fact, when the acid-test ratio is analysed, it is seen that although the current ratio is so high, the low current ratio indicates that the amount of inventories in the current assets of the enterprise is high and that the enterprise's inventory dependency is in question except for 2016. At this point, the quality of the enterprise's short-term solvency depends on the high inventory turnover rate. The fact that the cash ratio of the enterprise is below 0,20, which is an acceptable ratio, indicates that the enterprise may have difficulties in cash payments.

Table 7. Ersu Activity Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Receivable Turnover	2,6	6,39	4,32	1,92	3,22
Inventory Turnover	0,7	0,61	1,29	0,44	0,81
Trade Payables Turnover	1,71	5,25	5,12	1,3	1,77
Asset Turnover	0,17	0,19	0,27	0,17	0,3
Sector Receivables Turnov	7,97	9,08	10,01	8,61	8,65
Sector Inventory Turnover	9,13	9,31	7,98	8,03	7,9
Sector Trade PayableTurn	4,68	6,98	5,03	5,74	6,93
Sector Asset Turnover	1,17	1,12	1,06	0,95	0,91

It is observed that there is an unstable change in the operating ratios of the enterprise over the years. For example, while RT varies between 1.92 and 6.39, TPT varies between 1.30 and 5.25. Activity ratios are low compared to sector averages. Especially IT was realised below one except for 2018. The sector SIT was realised between 7.90 and 9.31. Since the acid-test ratio is less than one, it can be said that there is stock dependency and the inventory turnover rate is very low, and that the enterprise may have difficulties in paying debts in the short term despite the high current ratio. The company needs to develop policies that will realise the sale of its stocks more quickly.

Table 8. Ersu Financial Structure Ratios

Years	FLR	FR	ER	STFS	LTFS	FA/PCR	Sector FLR	Sector FR	Sector ER	Sector STFS	Sector LTFS	Sector FA/PCR
2016	0,16	5,39	0,84	0,06	0,1	0,78	0,69	1,69	0,63	0,49	0,2	0,75
2017	0,26	2,82	0,74	0,18	0,08	0,85	0,73	1,66	0,62	0,49	0,23	0,7
2018	0,28	2,61	0,72	0,19	0,09	0,83	0,73	1,27	0,56	0,51	0,21	0,77
2019	0,3	2,34	0,7	0,21	0,09	0,68	0,65	1,14	0,55	0,52	0,24	0,76
2020	0,26	2,8	0,74	0,18	0,08	0,68	0,64	1,56	0,65	0,49	0,22	0,77

Financial structure ratios show that the enterprise follows an equity-weighted financing policy within the financing structure. It can be said that the enterprise has used equity at the rate of 0.70 to 0.84 over the years and that the enterprise has a structure that is resistant to economic crises.

Table 9. Ersu Profitability Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Asset Profitability	0,0014	0,0264	0,0013	0,0697	0,0133
Equity Profitability	0,001	0,02	0,001	0,049	0,01
Sales Profitability	0,007	0,103	0,003	0,283	0,033
Sector Asset Profit.	0,125	0,11	0,134	0,234	0,22
Sector Equity Profit	0,05	0,053	0,06	0,081	0,138
Sector Sales Profit.	0,06	0,057	0,065	0,11	0,128

The profitability ratios of the company were low compared to the sector averages. The Company's return on sales was above the sector average in 2017 and 2019. The company needs to direct its assets to effective and efficient investments. One of the main reasons for the low sales profitability of the enterprise is the high production costs of the enterprise. The production cost of the enterprise varies between 0.90 and 0.98.

4.2.3. Kristal Kola ve Meşrubat Sanayi Ticaret A.Ş.

Table 10. Kristal Kola Liquidity Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Current Ratio	2,56	3,03	1,88	3,45	3,44
Acid-Test Ratio	2,18	2,62	1,37	2,7	2,45
Cash Rate	0,14	0,27	0,12	0,38	0,35
Sector Current Ratio	1,85	2,16	1,73	1,76	2,07
Sector Acid Test Rate	1,18	1,12	1,04	1,09	1,34
Sector Cash Ratio	0,06	0,22	0,22	0,27	0,57

The enterprise's current ratio ranges from 1.88 to 3.45. One may argue that the company's net working capital is too large. In actuality, it may be concluded that there are a lot of trade receivables and inventories inside current assets if the acid-test ratio is between 1.37 and 2.70. In 2019 and 2020, the company's cash ratio was high. For the business to use cash assets effectively and avoid idleness, it is crucial that the amount of cash is adequate. Operating ratios should also be taken into account in order to more precisely evaluate liquidity ratios.

Table 11. Kristal Kola Operating Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Receivable Turnover	2,98	2,77	2	2,63	3,14
Inventory Turnover	9,11	9,32	4,12	5,12	5,62
Trade Payables Turnover	6,65	6,51	3,89	4,64	6,84
Asset Turnover	1,13	0,89	0,68	0,86	1,07
Sector Receivables Turnover	7,97	9,08	10,01	8,61	8,65
Sector Inventory Turnover	9,13	9,31	7,98	8,03	7,9
Sector Trade Payables Turn.	4,68	6,98	5,03	5,74	6,93
Sector Asset Turnover	1,17	1,12	1,06	0,95	0,91

The company's RT and IT are low compared to the sector averages. Since a large part of the current asset amount consists of trade receivables and inventories, although the current ratio and acid-test ratio are very good, the company should evaluate its receivable collection policy and sales policy.

Table 12. Kristal Kola Financial Structure Ratios

Years							Sector	Sector	Sector	Sector	Sector	Sector
	FLR	FR	ER	STFS	LTFS	FA/PCR	FLR	FR	ER	STFS	LTFS	FA/PCR
2016	0,28	2,61	0,72	0,26	0,02	0,45	0,69	1,69	0,63	0,49	0,2	0,75
2017	0,37	1,73	0,63	0,21	0,16	0,46	0,73	1,66	0,62	0,49	0,23	0,7
2018	0,46	1,18	0,54	0,34	0,12	0,55	0,73	1,27	0,56	0,51	0,21	0,77
2019	0,27	2,64	0,73	0,21	0,07	0,36	0,65	1,14	0,55	0,52	0,24	0,76
2020	0,23	3,44	0,77	0,18	0,04	0,46	0,64	1,56	0,65	0,49	0,22	0,77

Using equity to finance asset investments is a top priority for the company. Self-funding asset purchase is crucial for the business's financing structure strength, but it's also critical for the enterprise to take advantage of the financial leverage impact, which means using debt to some degree because it's less expensive than stock.

Table 13. Kristal Kola Profitability Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Asset Profitability	0,045	0,039	-0,127	0,006	0,037
Equity Profitability	0,033	0,025	-0,069	0,004	0,029
Sales Profitability	0,03	0,03	-0,1	0	0,03
Sector Asset Profit.	0,125	0,11	0,134	0,234	0,22
Sector Equity Profit	0,05	0,053	0,06	0,081	0,138
Sector Sales Profit.	0,06	0,057	0,065	0,11	0,128

The AP, EP, and SP are below the industry average because the company does not employ financial leverage in resource utilization and does not make optimal use of its assets. The

company really produces with cost margins ranging from 0.86 to 0.91. The company should focus on investments that lower costs.

4.2.4. Pınar Su ve İçecek Sanayi ve Ticaret A.Ş.

Table 14. Pınar Su Liquidity Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Current Ratio	0,816	0,48	0,467	0,455	0,333
Acid-Test Ratio	0,619	0,451	0,36	0,353	0,256
Cash Rate	0,052	0,016	0,009	0,019	0,024
Sector Current Ratio	1,85	2,16	1,73	176	2,07
Sector Acid T.R.	1,18	1,12	1,04	1,09	1,34
Sector Cash Ratio	0,06	0,22	0,22	0,27	0,57

The current ratio of the enterprise between 2016 and 2020 is less than one. In other words, the net working capital of the enterprise is negative. Net working capital deficiency has gradually increased. This situation makes the continuity of the enterprise doubtful. The entity has problems in paying its short-term debts. Alternative ways should be used to pay short-term debts.

Table 15. Pınar Su Activity Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Receivable Turnover	8,22	7,99	7,53	6,59	6,7
Inventory Turnover	8,68	11,01	7,97	7	5,8
Trade Payables Turnover	2,18	2,58	2,72	2,36	2,27
Asset Turnover	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,69	0,52
Sector Receivables Turnov	7,97	9,08	10,01	8,61	8,65
Sector Inventory Turnover	9,13	9,31	7,98	8,03	7,9
Sector Trade Payab Turno	4,68	6,98	5,03	5,74	6,93
Sector Asset Turnover	1,17	1,12	1,06	0,95	0,91

RT and IT of the enterprise have been decreasing over the years. In an enterprise with inventory dependency and a current ratio less than one, it should be ensured that the operating cycle is as short as possible by increasing sales and selling inventories quickly and collecting receivables in a short time. Because the capital tied to raw materials remains tied until it returns to cash assets.

Table 16. Pınar Su Financial Structure Ratios

Years	FLR	FR	ER	STFS	LTFS	FA/PCR	Sector FLR	Sector FR	Sector ER	Sector STFS	Sector LTFS	Sector FA/PCR
2016	0,69	0,45	0,31	0,3	0,38	1,08	0,69	1,69	0,63	0,49	0,2	0,75
2017	0,74	0,35	0,26	0,42	0,32	1,33	0,73	1,66	0,62	0,49	0,23	0,7
2018	0,78	0,28	0,22	0,54	0,24	1,64	0,73	1,27	0,56	0,51	0,21	0,77
2019	0,84	0,19	0,16	0,53	0,31	1,61	0,65	1,14	0,55	0,52	0,24	0,76
2020	0,8	0,25	0,2	0,61	0,2	2,02	0,64	1,56	0,65	0,49	0,22	0,77

When the enterprise is evaluated, foreign resources were used in the acquisition of assets between 69% and 84%. This situation causes high interest expenses. It increases the borrowing costs of enterprises. The FA/PCR ratio of the enterprise is greater than one. In other words, the company utilised short-term foreign resources in the acquisition of fixed assets.

Table 17. Pınar Su Profitability Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Asset Profitability	-0,335	-0,308	-0,342	-0,634	-0,475
Equity Profitability	-0,104	-0,08	-0,075	-0,101	-0,094
Sales Profitability	-0,131	-0,099	-0,094	-0,146	-0,181
Sector Asset Profit.	0,125	0,11	0,134	0,234	0,22
Sector Equity Profit	0,05	0,053	0,06	0,081	0,138
Sector Sales Profit.	0,06	0,057	0,065	0,11	0,128

All profitability ratios of the enterprise have been negative for years.

4.2.5. Pınar Süt Mamulleri Sanayii A.Ş.

Table 18. Pınar Dairy Liquidity Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Current Ratio	1,2327	1,2106	1,0749	1,2308	1,1025
Acid-Test Ratio	0,8297	0,8068	0,717	0,8963	0,7905
Cash Rate	0,002	0,0037	0,0025	0,0328	0,0005
Sector Current Ratio	1,85	2,16	1,73	1,76	2,07
Sector Acid Test R.	1,18	1,12	1,04	1,09	1,34
Sector Cash Ratio	0,06	0,22	0,22	0,27	0,57

The current ratio of Pınar Dairy is greater than one in the 5-year period. However, it is generally desired that the ratio should be 2. Thus, while short-term debts are paid with half of the current assets, the enterprise can continue its activities with the remaining part. In other words, it is desired that the net working capital is positive. The net working capital of the enterprise is positive. However, the current ratio is well below two. In case the inventories, which have lower liquidity among current assets, cannot be sold or trade receivables cannot be collected, there is a possibility that short-term debts cannot be paid. As a matter of fact, the acid-test ratio was less than one in all periods under review. In other words, there is inventory dependency. The cash ratio of the company varies between 0.2% and 3%. Looking at the sector average, the cash ratio varies between 6% and 57%. There is a high probability that the company will have problems in cash payments.

Table 19. Pınar Dairy Operating Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Receivable Turnover	6,63	5,71	5,48	5,03	4,7
Inventory Turnover	8,12	7,15	7,42	9,26	8,15
Trade Payables Turnover	4,83	4,9	4,26	3,96	4,25
Asset Turnover	1,14	1,03	1,07	1,07	1,06

Sector Receivables Turnover	7,97	9,08	10,01	8,61	8,65
Sector Inventory Turnover	9,13	9,31	7,98	8,03	7,9
Sector Trade Payabl. Turnov.	4,68	6,98	5,03	5,74	6,93
Sector Asset Turnover	1,17	1,12	1,06	0,95	0,91

While RT of the enterprise is lower than the sector average, IT is in parallel with the sector average. Due to the fact that the acid-test ratio of the enterprise is less than one, the short-term solvency of the enterprise depends on the depletion of inventories through sales and collection if the sales made are on credit. In this sense, the fact that IT is in parallel with the sector average is a positive situation for the enterprise. It can be said that there is a balance between the collection period of trade receivables and the payment period of trade payables. The asset turnover rate of the company, i.e. the power of assets to generate sales, is above the sector average.

Table 20. Pınar Dairy Financial Structure Ratios

Years	FLR	FR	ER	STFS	LTFS	FA/PCR	Sector FLR	Sector FR	Sector ER	Sector STFS	Sector LTFS	Sector FA/PCR
2016	0,36	1,74	0,64	0,28	0,09	0,91	0,69	1,69	0,63	0,49	0,2	0,75
2017	0,43	1,35	0,57	0,3	0,13	0,91	0,73	1,66	0,62	0,49	0,23	0,7
2018	0,44	1,28	0,56	0,34	0,1	0,96	0,73	1,27	0,56	0,51	0,21	0,77
2019	0,42	1,38	0,58	0,3	0,12	0,9	0,65	1,14	0,55	0,52	0,24	0,76
2020	0,45	1,24	0,55	0,36	0,08	0,94	0,64	1,56	0,65	0,49	0,22	0,77

While the company has increased the rate of foreign resource utilisation in asset investment over time, it has decreased the equity ratio. However, the equity ratio still remained above 50 per cent. The capital structure of the enterprise is resistant to economic crises. The financing ratio also supports this. FA/PCR ratio is less than one. This is a desirable situation. A ratio less than one indicates that the permanent capital is sufficient for financing fixed assets.

Table 21. Pınar Dairy Profitability Ratios

Years	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Asset Profitability	0,101	0,068	0,063	0,039	0,038
Equity Profitability	0,064	0,039	0,035	0,022	0,021
Sales Profitability	0,056	0,038	0,033	0,021	0,02
Sector Asset Profit.	0,125	0,11	0,134	0,234	0,22
Sector Equity Profit	0,05	0,053	0,06	0,081	0,138
Sector Sales Profit.	0,06	0,057	0,065	0,11	0,128

The profitability ratios of the enterprise were positive. However, there has been a decrease in profitability ratios over time. Looking at the sector averages, it is seen that profitability ratios have increased over time. It can be said that the enterprise does not use its assets and equity resources efficiently enough. The enterprise needs to make asset investments that will increase the sales volume or use its existing assets effectively at full capacity.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

Financial statements are financial records that provide consumers the information they need to make choices at predetermined periods. The raw data in the financial accounts is transformed into knowledge that can be utilized for decision-making with the help of financial analysis techniques. Ratio analysis, trend analysis, horizontal analysis, and percentage analysis are the four types of financial statement analysis methodologies.

In order to make a general situation assessment, the companies in the beverage sector, which is a sub-sector of the main manufacturing sector, were examined as part of this study using the results of the analysis obtained from the statement of financial position and comprehensive income statements for the period 2016-2020.

The enterprises' ratios derived from the ratio analysis were assessed by contrasting them with the beverage industry's sector averages as determined by the Data Analysis Platform (DAP). The findings detailed in the study and described in broad strokes below are grouped and articulated when the sector averages are assessed in terms of liquidity ratios, activity ratios, financial structure ratios, and profitability ratios.

Liquidity Ratios: Coca-Cola İçecek A.Ş.'s current ratio was generally above 1.5 between 2016 and 2020, indicating that the company has sufficient current assets to pay its short-term debts. Kristal Kola and Ersu's current ratios decreased significantly, especially in 2018 and 2019. These decreases indicate insufficient working capital and liquidity risk.

Operating Ratios: Activity ratios provide information about the level of effective and efficient utilisation of assets of enterprises. They are the ratios that support the liquidity ratios of enterprises. Within the scope of the study, receivables turnover ratio (ADR), inventory turnover ratio (IPR), trade payables turnover ratio (TPA) and asset turnover ratio (ARO) are analysed as operating ratios. In terms of debt/equity ratio, Coca-Cola and Pınar Süt have a more corporate and balanced borrowing structure, while Kristal Kola's debt/equity ratio remained high throughout the period, indicating an increase in financial risk. In 2020, an increase in short-term debt burden was observed in all firms due to the pandemic.

Financial Structure Ratios: Financial structure ratios show the balance and distribution between liabilities and equity within the financing structure and provide information about the long-term solvency of the enterprise. While Coca-Cola is the most stable company in terms of inventory and receivable turnover rates, Kristal Kola experienced a significant decrease in inventory turnover rate, especially in 2019. This may indicate inefficiency in inventory management.

Profitability Ratios: Pınar Süt and Coca-Cola outperformed the sector average in terms of net profit margin and return on equity in the entire analysis period. Ersu and Kristal Kola, on the other hand, drew attention with their low profitability ratios in 2018 and 2020. Especially during the pandemic period, a serious decline was detected in Pınar Su's return on assets.

5.2. Recommendations

As part of the thesis, the situation was assessed using ratio analysis over beverage businesses listed on BIST between 2016 and 2020 using the comprehensive income statement and statement of financial condition. Owing to temporal limitations, the scope of the analysis was limited.

In terms of efficiency and profitability, it has been shown that businesses whose success graphs fall short of the sectoral averages have to look into the causes of these problems and decide to make better use of their resources.

It is believed that expanding the period range and the sector variety in subsequent research will both help to produce more thorough findings.

In conclusion, the evaluation of beverage companies operating in Borsa Istanbul using ratio analysis method is a valuable approach to understand their financial performance. Future research can make significant contributions to the knowledge in this field with more comprehensive data sets and advanced analysis methods.

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